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Abstract

This study explored relations among corporal punishment, perceived parental acceptance, and psychological adjustment of adolescents in Bangladesh. A sample of 754 students (46.3% female) aged 9 to 18 from 13 schools across Dhaka, Rangpur, and Chittagong completed Bangla versions of five standardized questionnaires. Hierarchical regression analyses revealed that perceived paternal acceptance completely mediated the relations of both perceived harshness and justness of fathers' punishment with youth's psychological adjustment. Conversely, maternal acceptance completely mediated the relation between perceived justness of punishment and adjustment, but only partially mediated the relation regarding maternal harshness. Maternal harshness continued to make a unique, independent contribution to psychological maladjustment beyond the substantial contribution of maternal acceptance. Overall, the findings demonstrate that while physical punishment is judged as slightly harsh but justified, parental acceptance remains the primary, critical predictor of positive adolescent psychological outcomes.

Keywords: Corporal punishment; Parental acceptance-rejection; Psychological adjustment-maladjustment; Adolescents in Bangladesh

Relations among Corporal Punishment, Perceived Parental Acceptance, and Psychological Adjustment of Child and Adolescent in Bangladesh

Muhammad Kamal Uddin*

Abstract

This study explored relations among corporal punishment, perceived parental acceptance, and psychological adjustment of adolescents in Bangladesh. Seven hundred fifty four (46.3% female), 4th through 10th grade students between the ages of 9 to 18 years ($M = 12.71$, $SD = 1.97$) were recruited from thirteen schools in Dhaka, Rangpur, and Chittagong districts of Bangladesh. Bangla language versions of five questionnaires and a demographic form were used to collect data. These included the youth versions of the Physical Punishment Questionnaire for mothers and for fathers, the child versions (short form) of the Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire for mothers and for fathers, the child version of the Personality Assessment Questionnaire, and the Personal Information Form. Results of hierarchical regression analyses showed that perceived paternal acceptance completely mediated the relations of both perceived harshness and justness of fathers' punishment with youth's psychological adjustment. The story about maternal acceptance was somewhat different. Perceived maternal acceptance completely mediated the relation between perceived justness of punishment and youths' psychological adjustment. However, maternal acceptance only partially mediated the relation between harshness of mothers' punishment and youth's psychological adjustment. Maternal harshness continued to make a very small but independent contribution to psychological adjustment over and above the greater contribution made by perceived maternal acceptance.

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Keywords : Corporal punishment; parental acceptance - rejection; psychological adjustment-maladjustment

Relations among Corporal Punishment, Perceived Parental Acceptance, and Psychological Adjustment of Child and Adolescent in Bangladesh

Physical punishment is the use of direct or indirect infliction of physical discomfort or pain on a child by a person in a position of authority over the child (e.g., parent) usually for the purpose of (1) stopping a child's unwanted behavior, (2) preventing the reoccurrence of unwanted behavior, or (3) because the child failed to do something s/he was supposed to do (Rohner, 2005). It takes place at home, in care homes, schools and institutions, on the streets, and at workplaces. Corporal punishment occurs mostly on child and adolescent. It is used in more than 75% of the world's societies (Barry, Josephson, Lauer, & Marshall, 1977; Ember & Ember, 2005; Levinson, 1989) and it is used "frequently" in only 20% of the societies (Levinson, 1981, 1989). Parents in about 82% of societies more often resort to exhorting and setting an example of appropriate behavior as child-rearing techniques (Barry et al., 1977).

Despite the fact that corporal punishment is used globally, there is a growing debate among researchers over the use of corporal punishment. One group who supports an "anticorporal punishment view" (i.e., detractors) contended that significant empirical evidence suggests that physical punishment has negative developmental consequences for children (Gershoff, 2002; Holden, 2002). Indeed, Straus (1994) argued all forms of physical punishment—under all conditions—have detrimental consequences for short-term and long-term developmental outcomes. Other group argued that mild to moderate forms of corporal punishment such as normative spanking—especially in loving families—may not have negative consequences and may, under some conditions, even have beneficial effects (Baumrind, 1996a; Larzelere, 2000). The latter group of researchers can be characterized as "conditional defenders" of corporal punishment. They argued that the effects of spanking may be positive, negative, or both depending on the conditions in which it occurs. Overall, then, conditional defenders and detractors of corporal punishment agree that the use of severe or frequent punishment as the primary form of parental discipline should be

discouraged. These researchers disagree completely, however, over the use of such mild to moderate forms of corporal punishment as ordinary or normative spanking (Baumrind, 2003).

Research in various cultures clarifies that children's perception of physical punishment as a form of parental love, withdrawal or rejection accounts for many effects on child outcomes. One study reported that the harshness of caregiver punishment correlated very strongly with psychological maladjustment (Rohner, Kean, & Cournoyer, 1991). Another study on American youths has evidenced that perceived harshness and perceived unjustness of punishment were more strongly correlated with youths' perceptions of caregiver acceptance-rejection than with youths' psychological adjustment (Rohner, Bourque, & Elordi, 1996). A Puerto Rican study on youths has reported that perceived unfairness of punishment and caregivers' use of explanation were more strongly correlated with youths' perceptions of caregiver acceptance-rejection than with youths' psychological adjustment (Matos & Rohner, 2004). Empirical findings from these studies indicate that the effects of corporal punishment tend to be dependent (mediated) to a significant degree on youths' perception of punishment as an expression of parental acceptance-rejection.

Research on moderators such as parent-child relationships is very less in number. Simons et al. (2000) tested two models to predict conduct problems in American and Taiwanese adolescents. Results indicated that corporal punishment and parental acceptance had significant effects on conduct problems for youths. Similarly, in a 6-year longitudinal study of European American, African American, and Latino children, researchers found a significant moderator effect of maternal emotional support on the relation between punishment and behavior problems. Several studies concluded that race and/or ethnicity seems to moderate the effect of physical discipline on behavior (Deater-Deckard, Dodge, Bates, & Pettit, 1996; Lansford, Deater-Deckard, Dodge, Bates, & Pettit, 2003). Other studies, for example, on White and African American (Rohner et al., 1996) and Latino (McLoyd & Smith, 2002) youths, failed to confirm such findings.

Even though a host of empirical evidences are available on corporal punishment, little is documented about the issue from the cultural context of Bangladesh. Recently, UNICEF (2008) has focused mainly on form, frequency, severity and other aspects of punishment surveying a sample of 3840 children of Bangladesh between the ages of 9 through 18 years. It also showed that the children perceived the punishment negative.

However, the survey tells nothing about the possible consequences of corporal punishment on children's behavioral outcomes. Therefore, it is the objective of the present study to explore possible relations of corporal punishment with perceptions of parental acceptance and psychological adjustment of child and adolescent in Bangladesh.

Methods

Sample

This research was conducted on a sample of 754 (53.8% male and 46.2% female), 4th through 10th grade students recruited from 13 schools of the 3 cities of Bangladesh. While the schools were selected purposively the respondents within each school were selected

conveniently. Out of the respondents 70% were from Dhaka, the capital city of Bangladesh, approximately 22% were from Chittagong, the commercial capital of Bangladesh, and approximately 8% were from Rangpur. Their ages ranged from 9 to 18 years with a mean age of 12.71 years and a standard deviation of 1.97. Vast majority of the respondents (90.6%) identified themselves as middle class background. About two-third (62.6%) of the respondents reported their mothers as homemakers and the rest 36.9% as service-holders (.5% missing); 55% reported their fathers to be service-holders, 40.2% businessmen, 2% farmers, and 2% labors (.8% missing). The other sample characteristics are shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Distribution of sample by academic grade, maternal and paternal education (N = 754)

Variable	N	%
Academic Grade		
Four	57	7.6
Five	91	12.1
Six	212	28.1
Seven	102	13.5
Eight	99	13.1
Nine	96	12.7
Ten	97	12.9

Maternal Education

None	18	2.4
Primary (1-5)	189	25.1
Secondary (6-8)	167	22.1
Higher Secondary (9-12)	101	13.4
Graduate (13-14/15/16)	76	10.1
Masters	77	10.2
PhD	19	2.5
Missing	107	14.2

Paternal Education

None	9	1.2
Primary (1-5)	82	10.9
Secondary (6-8)	107	14.2
Higher Secondary (9-12)	160	21.2
Graduate (13-14/15/16)	117	15.5
Masters	128	17.0
PhD	53	7.0
Missing	98	13

Measures

The present study required the following five questionnaires and a demographic form: (1 and 2) the youth versions of the Physical Punishment Questionnaire for mothers and for fathers (Youth PPQ: Mother and Father); (3 and 4) the child versions (short form) of the Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire for mothers and for fathers (Child PARQ: Mother and Father); (5) the child version of the Personality Assessment

Questionnaire (Child PAQ); and (6), the Personal Information Form (PIF), for demographic information. Each measure is described more fully below.

PPQ. Bangla version (Uddin, Zaman, & Semul 2012) of the PPQ was used for the current investigation (Rohmer, 2001; Rohmer, Ripoll-Nunez, Moodie, & Ruan, 2005). The 26 items of this self-report questionnaire assesses youths' perceptions of their current experiences of corporal punishment. The measure

contains a variety of response options used for different items. Children who were physically punished at the hands of their mothers (major female caregivers) and fathers (major male caregivers) were asked to make overall judgments about nine issues related to their experiences of corporal punishment. These issues are (a) overall frequency of punishment received (i.e. how often was the respondent punished?); (b) overall severity of punishment received (i.e. how hard or severe does the punishment tend to be?); (c) consistency of punishment (i.e. does the caregiver sometimes punish a given misbehavior and sometimes not?); (d) predictability of punishment received (i.e. when respondents are punished, can they tell or predict from one time to another whether they will be punished?); (e) overall incidents of punishment received (i.e. how many times in any given week does the respondent tend to be punished?); (f) perceived fairness of punishment received (i.e. as a general rule, to what extent does the respondent feel the punishment is fair?); (g) perceived deservedness of punishment received (i.e. as a general rule, to what extent does the respondent feel the punishment is deserved?); (h) timing of punishment received (i.e. is the punishment administered at the moment the parent discovered the youth has done something wrong, or is it delayed for a period of time?); and (i) parents use of explanation or reasoning (i.e. to what

extent does the caregiver explain to the youth before punishing them – what they did that was wrong and why it was wrong?).

The PPQ, in addition to these nine theoretical issues, asks about 13 more specific forms of punishment that they may have experienced at-least once. These are spanking, slapping, shoving, beating severely with an object that leaves a mark, welt, or bruise and hitting firmly but not severely with an object that leaves no mark, welt or bruise. The questionnaire again asks respondents to volunteer up to four other forms of punishment they may have experienced at least once.

Frequency of punishment correlates positively with severity of punishment in most studies. Similarly, fairness and deservedness of punishment generally correlate positively. Researchers sum the two scores to create a composite measure of perceived harshness and justness (which can spread from a low of 2 through a high of 9, from a low of 2 through a high of 8, respectively) of punishment. The higher the score is on the harshness and the justness variables, youths perceive the punishment to be harsher and more just respectively. Alpha coefficients for the portion of study were .47 and .61 for maternal and paternal harshness; .39 and .42 for maternal and paternal justness.

PARQ. To assess youths' perceptions about current parental (maternal and paternal) acceptance and rejection the Bangla version (Uddin, 2011) of Child PARQ/Short Form (Rohner, 2005) was used. The Mother and Father versions of the Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire (short form) are almost identical 24-item 4-point Likert type self-report measures assessing respondents' perceptions of the warmth/affection, hostility/aggression, indifference/neglect, and undifferentiated rejection they now experience at the hands of their mothers and fathers (Child PARQ). Examples of test items on the both version of the PARQ Short Form include "My mother/father makes me feel wanted and needed" (perceived warmth or affection); "My mother/father goes out of her/his way to hurt my feelings" (perceived hostility or aggression); "My mother/father ignores me as long as I do to bother her/him" (perceived indifference or neglect); "My mother/father does not really love me" (perceived undifferentiated rejection).

The sum of the four PARQ scales (with the warmth/affection scale reverse-scored to create a measure of coldness/lack of affection) constitutes a robust measure of overall perceived maternal and paternal acceptance-rejection. The possible scale score ranges from a low of 24 to a high of 96. Score at or above the scale midpoint 60 represents more

parental rejection than acceptance as perceived by the offspring. The lower is the total PARQ score than the scale midpoint 60 the higher is the more parental acceptance than rejection as perceived by the offspring. The PARQ has been used in over 400 studies worldwide and is known to have outstanding reliability and validity for use in cross-cultural research (Khaleque & Rohner, 2002; Rohner, 2005, 2011). Alpha coefficient for the Mother PARQ was .82 and for the Father PARQ was .82.

PAQ. The Bangla version (Uddin & Ahmed, 2012) of child PAQ (Rohner & Khaleque, 2005) was used to measure youths' overall psychological adjustment. The child version of the Personality Assessment Questionnaire is a 42-item self-report questionnaire assessing the form of psychological adjustment believed to be universally associated with perceived parental acceptance and rejection (Rohner, 2004). This form of psychological adjustment (or maladjustment) is defined by seven personality dispositions measured on the PAQ as consequences of perceived rejection. They include: (1) hostility/aggression, passive aggression, or problems with the management of hostility and aggression; (2) dependence or defensive independence depending on form, frequency, severity, timing, and longevity of perceived rejection; (3) feelings of impaired self-esteem;

(4) feelings of impaired self-adequacy; (5) emotional unresponsiveness; 6) emotional instability; and 7) negative worldview. The PAQ has been used successfully in several hundred studies internationally, and it has been shown to have excellent reliability and validity for use in cross-cultural research (Khaleque & Rohner, 2002; Rohner & Khaleque, 2005).

Some of the sample items on the measure are "I think about fighting or being unkind" (hostility or aggression); "I like myself" (positive self-esteem); "I can compete successfully for the things I want" (positive self-adequacy); "It's easy for me to show my friends that I really like them" (emotional responsiveness); "I am cheerful and happy one minute and gloomy or unhappy the next" (emotional instability); "I think the world is a good, happy place" (positive world view). The possible scale score ranges from a low of 42 to a high of 210. Psychological maladjustment is indicated if the total PAQ score is at or above the scale midpoint 105. On the other hand, psychological adjustment is indicated if the total PAQ score is below the scale midpoint 105.

The child PAQ, which is available in more than 20 languages, has been used in many studies cross-culturally. From these studies, a large body of evidence summarized in Rohner and Khaleque (2005) showing the measure

to be reliable and valid for use in cross-cultural research. Coefficient alpha for the current study was .79.

PIF. The PIF elicited demographic, personal, and social information that included respondent's gender, age, grade in school, academic achievement, number of siblings, birth order, family size, parental education, parental occupation, family socioeconomic status, religious affiliation, etc.

Procedure

A written permission to collect data was received from principals of respective schools. Following permission, three standardized self-report questionnaires and one personal information form attached to the top of the questionnaires were administered in classroom settings. Before the administration, necessary rapport was established with respondents. Respondents were asked to complete the questionnaires at their own paces. Respondents were assured that their responses will be kept confidential and that there is nothing like right or wrong responses to any question. Finally, respondents were encouraged to ask questions coming in their minds during the task and they were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. It took one hour on average to complete the task. After the completion, every respondent received a token gift

with thanks for their cooperation and participation in the study.

Results

Means and standard deviations were computed for boys and girls to describe

their perceptions of parental punishment, parental acceptance, and psychological adjustment. Also *t* value was calculated to test the significance of gender differences in those variables. The results are shown in Table 2.

Mean, Standard Deviation, and Independent *t* testing the significance of differences between boys (*n* =406) and girls (*n* =348) in punishment, acceptance, and psychological adjustment

Variable	Girls		Boys		t
	M	SD	M	SD	
Maternal Punishment					
Punishment Sum	5.91	3.62	5.75	3.86	0.57
Harshness	5.37	1.67	5.44	1.88	-0.56
Justness	5.22	1.48	5.42	1.37	-1.96
Paternal Punishment					
Punishment Sum	4.68	2.80	4.98	2.96	-1.45
Harshness	4.72	1.82	5.32	1.65	-4.74***
Justness	5.24	1.44	5.35	1.32	-1.16
Maternal Acceptance	45.74	11.49	45.74	11.15	0.00
Paternal Acceptance	45.41	11.44	45.84	11.46	-0.52
Psychological Adjustment	93.78	14.36	93.95	14.85	-0.15

p* < .05, ** *p* < .01, * *p* < .001

Results in Table 2 revealed that child and adolescent experienced on average more than five forms of punishment at the hands of their mothers (*M* = 5.91 for girls and *M* = 5.75 for boys) and more than four forms at the hands of

their fathers (*M* = 4.68 for girls and *M* = 4.98 for boys). They perceived their punishment as 'moderately harsh' (*M* = 5.37 for girls and *M* = 5.44 for boys in case of maternal punishment; *M* = 4.72 for girls and *M* = 5.32 for boys in

case of paternal punishment). However, they tended to feel that the punishment they received was "fairly justified" (see Table 2 for details). Thus, whereas physical punishment was judged as being slightly harsh overall, it tended to be viewed as being justified. With regard to perceived acceptance, youths reported both mothers ($M = 45.74$ for girls and $M = 45.74$ for boys) and fathers ($M = 45.41$ for girls and $M = 45.84$ for boys) to be fairly loving or accepting overall. With regard to psychological adjustment, youths reported themselves to be fairly psychologically adjusted ($M = 93.78$ for girls and $M = 93.95$ for boys). Finally, independent sample t tests revealed significant gender differences only in harshness of paternal punishment; boys receiving harsher discipline than girls.

However, no such trend was observed either in maternal punishment or in psychological adjustment.

Further, paired t values were computed to see the differences between father and mother's behavior in punishment and acceptance. Table 3 showed that mothers used significantly greater forms of punishment ($M = 5.82$) than did fathers ($M = 4.84$). Also, punishment at the hands of mothers was perceived to be harsher ($M = 5.41$ for mothers and $M = 4.84$ for fathers). However, no significant differences between father and mother were observed in justness or in acceptance. In other words, fathers and mothers were perceived to be equally accepting and their punishment was perceived to be equally justified.

Table 3

Mean, Standard Deviation, and Paired t testing the significance of differences between father and mother's behavior

Variable	Mothers' Behavior		Fathers' Behavior		t
	M	SD	M	SD	
Punishment Sum	5.82	3.75	4.84	2.89	10.48***
Harshness of Punishment	5.41	1.79	5.04	1.76	5.11***
Justness of Punishment	5.32	1.42	5.30	1.36	0.47
Parental Acceptance	45.74	11.30	45.64	11.45	0.26

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

To explore possible relations of punishment with parental acceptance and psychological adjustment, simple correlations were computed. Table 4 showed that

harshness and justness of both maternal and paternal punishment were correlated significantly with youths' psychological adjustment. In addition, both perceived maternal and paternal acceptance were significantly correlated with youths' psychological adjustment.

Table 4

Matrix of correlations among youths' self-reports of parental punishment, parental acceptance, and psychological adjustment (N = 754)

Variable				
Harshness				
Justness				
Parental Acceptance				
Psychological Adjustment				

Note. Coefficients above the diagonal pertain to mothers' behavior; those below the diagonal pertain to fathers' behavior. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

To explore possible unique and joint contributions of perceived parental acceptance and punishment to youths' psychological adjustment, I tested two sets of hierarchical multiple regression models. The first, summarized in Table 5, assessed the relation between mothers' behavior and youths' adjustment; the second, summarized in Table 6, assessed the relation between fathers' behavior and youths' adjustment. In both, youths' age and gender were entered in step 1 (Model 1) as possible covariates. In step 2 (Model 2), perceived acceptance, harshness of punishment, and justness of

punishment were added to the regression equations. Results displayed in Tables 5 and 6 showed that youths' age contributed significantly to variations in youths' psychological adjustment. Both tables also showed that perceived parental (both paternal and maternal) acceptance made the greatest contribution to youths' adjustment. Justness of perceived maternal and paternal punishment no longer made significant contributions to youths' adjustment when the influence of perceived acceptance and harshness of punishment were controlled. Accordingly, justness of punishment

was dropped from further analyses. Harshness of punishment, however, made a very small but unique contribution to youths' adjustment. Thus, for fathers, only perceived acceptance contributed to offspring's psychological adjustment. But both mothers' and fathers' acceptance made a minor extent—harshness of maternal punishment and independent contributions to offspring's adjustment.

Table 5

Summary of hierarchical regression analysis for maternal psychological adjustment (N = 500)

	B	SE
Step 1		
Constant	75.64	3.66
Age	1.50	.27
Gender	-.54	1.05
Step 2		
Constant	59.23	4.52
Age	.70	.25
Gender	-.36	.94
Maternal Harshness	.68	.27
Maternal Justness	-.34	.34
Maternal Acceptance	.53	.04

Note. R² = .04 for Step 1, R² = .19 for Step 2 (p < .001). *p < .05.

Table 6

Summary of hierarchical regression analysis for paternal psychological adjustment (N = 754)

	B	SE
Step 1		
Constant	75.64	3.66
Age	1.50	.27
Gender	-.54	1.05

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was dropped from further analyses. Harshness of maternal (but not paternal) punishment, however, made a very small but unique contribution to adjustment. Thus, for fathers, only perceived acceptance contributed significantly and uniquely to offspring's psychological adjustment. But both maternal acceptance and—to a minor extent—harshness of maternal punishment appeared to make significant and independent contributions to offspring' adjustment.

Table 5

Summary of hierarchical regression analysis for maternal variables predicting youths' psychological adjustment (N = 500)

	B	SE	B
Step 1			
Constant	75.64	3.66	
Age	1.50	.27	.20***
Gender	-.54	1.05	-.02
Step 2			
Constant	59.23	4.55	
Age	.70	.25	.09**
Gender	-.36	.94	-.01
Maternal Harshness	.68	.27	.08*
Maternal Justness	-.34	.34	-.03
Maternal Acceptance	.53	.04	.41***

Note. $R^2 = .04$ for Step 1, $R^2 = .19$ for Step 2 ($p < .001$). * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 6

Summary of hierarchical regression analysis for paternal variables predicting youths' psychological adjustment (N = 754)

	B	SE	β
Step 1			
Constant	75.64	3.66	
Age	1.50	.27	.20***
Gender	-.54	1.05	-.02

Step 2

Constant	60.74	4.28	
Age	.50	.24	.07
Gender	.15	.93	.01
Paternal Harshness	.42	.27	.05
Paternal Justness	-.67	.34	-.06
Paternal Acceptance	.61	.04	.48***

Note. $R^2 = .04$ for Step 1, $R^2 = .24$ for Step 2 ($p < .001$). * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Because perceived maternal acceptance significantly correlated with perceived paternal acceptance ($r = .52, p < .01$), it seemed possible that the apparently unique contribution of both mothers' and fathers' acceptance to youths' adjustment might be an artifact of this correlation. To test this possibility, I performed a simultaneous multiple regression, entering age, paternal acceptance, maternal acceptance, and maternal harshness into the equation as predictors of youths' psychological adjustment. Table 7 showed that both maternal and paternal acceptance continued to make direct but independent contributions to variations in youths' psychological adjustment. Age and harshness of maternal punishment no longer contributed significantly when the influence of parental (both mothers' and fathers') acceptance was controlled. The coefficient of multiple correlation for the entire sample was .57, indicating that the linear combination of parental (both father and mother) acceptance, age, and maternal harshness accounted for 32.8% variance in youths' psychological adjustment. However, maternal and paternal acceptance can jointly account for 32.2%.

Table 7

Summary of simultaneous regression analysis for maternal acceptance, maternal harshness, paternal acceptance and youths' psychological adjustment (N = 754)

	B	SE	β	R^2
Constant	50.88	3.22		
Age	.33	.23	.05	
Maternal Acceptance	.32	.05	.25***	.328***
Maternal Harshness	.50	.26	.06	
Paternal Acceptance	.47	.05	.37***	

* $p < .05$, *** $p < .001$

Discussion

The main objective of the present study was to explore: (a) whether perceived harshness and justness of corporal punishment were associated with variations in youths' psychological adjustment and (b) whether the relationship between parental punishment and youths' adjustment were mediated through youths' perceptions of parental (maternal and paternal) acceptance. Results of correlation analyses revealed that the harsher or more unjust youths experienced corporal punishment to be, the less accepted they felt themselves to be. And, the less accepted the youths felt themselves to be, the more psychologically maladjusted they reported themselves to be. These findings are fairly consistent with past studies (Erkman & Rohner, 2006; Rohner, Bourque, & Elordi, 1996; Rohner, Kean, & Cournoyer, 1991; Matos & Rohner, 2004; Rohner, Khaleque, & Cournoyer, 2005).

Results of regression analyses revealed that age contributed significantly to variations in youths' adjustment. This finding is consistent with Uddin (2011) who observed that age is significantly related to self-concept, anxiety, depression, anger, and disruptive behavior. The higher is the age of the boys and girls the lower is the self-concept, the higher is the anxiety, depression, anger, and (for boys)

disruptive behavior. Results further revealed that neither harshness nor justness of paternal punishment made a significant contribution to variations in youths' psychological adjustment when the influence of perceived paternal acceptance was controlled. However, the picture was somewhat different for maternal punishment; only perceived harshness (but not justness) of maternal punishment had small but direct effect on youths' psychological adjustment when the influence of perceived maternal acceptance was controlled. These findings are consistent with several past studies (Erkman & Rohner, 2006; Khaleque & Rohner, 2002; Rohner, 2004; Rohner & Britner, 2002). Thus, perceived parental acceptance emerged in this study as unique and significant predictors of youths' adjustment; vis-à-vis the harshness of maternal punishment had a small but direct effect on youths' adjustment. This finding supported assertions by Straus (2003) and others who claimed that all forms of physical punishment—regardless of other possibly mediating or moderating factors—have detrimental effects on children's development. This held true at least for harshness of maternal punishment.

This study had several strengths. Firstly, it examined the influence of third variables e. g., parental acceptance, youths' gender and age on the relation between

punishment and child outcomes which have been suggested in several studies (Baumrind, Larzelere, & Cowan, 2002; Benjet & Kazdin, 2003; Gershoff, 2002; Holden, 2002; Parke, 2002; Ripoll-Núñez & Rohner, 2006). Secondly, Gershoff and others suggested that youths' perceptions should be considered with regard to their own personal experiences of punishment—rather than relying on the reports of others—as has been done in most other studies. Thirdly, younger children are punished more often than older (as reported in Erkman & Rohner, 2006). The participants included in the study covered a broad range of ages.

Children below 9 years were approached in this study but they were eventually excluded since they felt difficulty in comprehending the questionnaires. Fourthly, the sample size is large enough and participants included in the study were from three divisional cities of the country. So, generalization can be made based on the study. However, the study is limited by its cross-sectional research design, as is true to all but a very few studies. As a result, without evidence from a longitudinal study, it is difficult to draw causal inferences about relations among corporal punishment, perceived acceptance, and youths' adjustment.

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